

General challenges
regarding data sharing –
building blocks that need to
be in place

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1 Trust

You need trust to succeed!

Different kinds of trust and levels

1.

- **Data for supervision, control, penalties, compliance etc** – high quality data, individual data (i.e. epizooty)
- **Data for statistics** – good enough data, aggregated data (i.e. antibiotic resistance)

2.

Trust between actors – B2G, G2G, C2G etc, altruism (Data Governance Act)

2 Data

You need data to succeed!

But you also need to understand your data sets to succeed.

I picture myself a pantry with shelves. On the shelves there are jars with a certain content. Your job is to put labels on the jars and describe the contents.

Examples of labels:

- **Complete data set or only a sample?**
- **Quality** – How well suited is a dataset to serve its specific purpose?
- **Quantity** – Do you have enough data?
- **Accessible** – Do you have access to the data stored? (legislation/agreement)
- **Interoperability** – Real time data exchange (legislation G2G)
- **Validity** – check the quality before using (time)
- **Personal data / non personal data**
- **Commercial data / business secrets**

3 Legal compliance

How to get the data!

A. Legal requirement by law = you must share + how and why (purpose) to share is regulated by law + non-disclosure legislation between agencies (G2G, B2G, C2G)

B. Voluntary agreement (G2G) + consent from citizen/business (if personal data/commercial data)

New EU-legislation is coming (Data Governance Act + Data Act)

The structure of legislation data sharing (“incomplete and not coherent”) - EU talks about the decade of data, lots of new horizontal data legislation during 2023

New EU legislation 2022/23

Data Governance Act

Digital Services Act

Data Act

AI-Act

E-Privacy Act

Digital Markets Act

European Digital Identity

4 Business value

Sharing data is not for free

There is always a cost associated with sharing data
– you cannot just take it

Personal data – commercial data – governance data

Legal requirement/Agreement

- **Donate for free / altruism (citizen + business)**
- **Allocation in budget (agency)**
- **Standard fee / lump sum**
- **Cost recovery**

5 Security

How about security?

It is not only about fire walls, connection, encryption etc.

Closed – share with (different) friends – open

How much data can you share securely? I.e. the conflict between open data and closed national security data. Small parts of innocent data sets can become dangerous together.

Who is protected by the legislation? I.e. the Swedish Patient Data Act protects the patient, not the next patient (i.e. training data for algorithms).

6 Infrastructure

Where is the data stored?

Inside/outside EU?

- **EU goal – to build European data infrastructure**

7 Meta Data

Information about the data

It takes time

Who are you calling?

Who can decide about the data?

How transfer knowledge?

Education about how to use the data /system?

How do you search?

8 Skills

Do you have the right skills?

So you have the data but can you use the data? What skills do you bring to the partnership?

- **Analytics functions**
- **Data integration developers**
- **Data management**
- **Data support**
- **Domain & technical expertise**
- **Legal**

Thank you!

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